

HIGH PERFORMANCE SELF-REINFORCED POLYLACTIC ACID BIOCOSITES WITH DEGRADATION SENSING

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Abstract

In this paper a new family of self-reinforced polymers (SRPs) are being described which are based on the biopolymer polylactic acid (PLA). The concept is based on high strength PLA tapes in combination with a thin outer adhesive layer based on a lower melting temperature PLA filled with carbon nanotubes (CNTs), and which are fused together using a compression moulding technique into a 'brick-and-mortar' structure. A biodegradable biobased engineering plastic with improved mechanical properties and the potential to sense biodegradation is obtained. The influence of solid-state drawing and post-drawing temperature on the mechanical properties of the PLA tapes has been investigated. The Young's modulus and tensile strength for tapes drawn at 130 °C are 6.7 GPa and 280 MPa, respectively. Compared to isotropic PLA films, a 3.7 and 5.2 times increase in Young's modulus and tensile strength has been achieved. CNTs were introduced in PLA matrix in order to develop a smart composite system that can sense biodegradation.

1. Introduction

Environmental legislation, public concern, and waste management are all increasing the pressure on manufactures of materials and end-products to consider the environmental impact of their products at all stages of their life cycle. At this moment, 'eco-design' or 'designing for recycling' must be an important part of our daily lives if we are to preserve the natural resources of our planet. The automotive industry, in particular, is now trying to make every component recyclable because of a new European Union (EU) directive on the end-of-life of vehicles (ELV). This states that by 2015 vehicles must be made of 95% recyclable materials, of which 85% can be recovered through reuse or mechanical recycling and 10% through energy recovery or thermal recycling.

Glass fiber reinforced polypropylene (PP) composites are currently widely used to make car parts. However, these materials often suffer from significant loss in mechanical properties during recycling and further use in critical applications may be limited. Current trends focus on the use of natural

fibers like flax and hemp as alternatives to glass fiber. Although these fibers have some ecological advantages since they are renewable, the relatively poor thermal stability may lead to severe additional thermal degradation during subsequent recycling or reprocessing steps.

One promising approach is "self-reinforced polymer" composites (SRPs) or "all-polymer" composites [1, 2], in which a polymer matrix is reinforced with oriented fibres or tapes, or particles of the same polymer. This technology makes the end product much stronger and stiffer without any weight gain. SRPs have been developed to replace traditional fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) with high volume fraction of reinforcement (~ 90%), a better interfacial adhesion, and enhanced recyclability. In previous work, our group co-developed technology based around PP [3, 4], which is now commercialized under the names of PURE® and Tegriss®. Following on from these successes our research into all-polymer composites has moved towards other polymer systems such as polyethylene (PE) [5], poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) [6], cellulose [7] and aramid [8].

In this work, a new family of SRPs is being presented which are based on the biopolymer polylactic acid (PLA), which can be used for (semi-) structural applications such as automotive, general engineering or consumer product markets with improved performances (mechanical and electrical), functionalities (sensing properties), durability, cost performance and processability. The main advantages of using biopolymers is to create these performance products from sustainable resources, competing with fossil hydrocarbon sourced polymers, at the same time leaving open the possibility of biodegradability and composting as an alternative end-of-life option in addition to mechanical recycling and incineration (see Fig. 1).

The concept is based on PLA reinforcement tapes and a thin layer of PLA matrix, which are combined using a film-stacking technique into a ‘brick-and-mortar’ structure (see Fig. 2). The reinforcing tape is solid-state drawn under tension at temperatures below the melting point of the polymer to orient the polymer chains along the tape’s axis to improve strength and stiffness. This layer is then sandwiched between two thin outer layers of a PLA matrix specially formulated with a lower melting point than the reinforcing core. During hot-pressing, the matrix layers are selectively melted to weld the high-strength PLA tapes together to form a composite structure, while retaining the mechanical properties of the core component of the tape.

The obtained SR-PLA holds very strong future promise for potential applications as high-performance biodegradable materials. However, there are two important questions for the final product in the real applications. First of all, how long will it be used? Is there any degradation during the product’s life time? Secondly, if degradation does occur, can we monitor the degradation levels during the usage and how can we easily realize it?

Insertion of conductive nanoparticles, such as carbon black [9], metal powder [10], or carbon fibre [11], within insulating polymer matrices generates a new species of smart materials termed “conductive polymer nanocomposites (CPCs)”. These intelligent materials can be used for self-regulating heating devices or for sensor design. Electronic conduction in CPCs is achieved through various processes, of which the most important definitely are ohmic conduction, due to direct contact between nanofillers, and tunneling conduction, taking place

when electrons can circulate through a small insulating barrier. Therefore, it is easy to imagine that a change in conductivity could be induced by deforming the infinite filler network. The deformation or break-down of the composite percolation network can be introduced by external stimuli such as temperature [12], gases [13], vapour [14], mechanical stress and strain [15], pH value [16], liquid [17], etc. In other words, the conductivity of CPCs can respond to outer stimuli.

In present study, through the introduction of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and formation of conductive networks, the PLA matrix was used for sensing biodegradation to introduce added functionality to the composite. Here we try to use the evolution of electrical conductivity as a means to monitor PLA degradation. The morphology of the polymer changes during degradation, which leads to a change of the filler network, resulting in a change in electrical conductivity of the nanocomposite. Therefore, through the evolution of the electrical conductivity signal during PLA degradation, we will be able to correlate the change of electrical conductivity of the PLA composites with the degradation level of the polymer.

2. Experimental

2.1 Production of PLA reinforcement tapes

Collin single screw extruder was employed to obtain PLA Natureworks 4032D extruded tapes. Due to extrusion, it is likely that some orientation was already present in the tapes before subsequent drawing, but this is ignored in this study since the reported draw ratios are merely comparative. The extruded tape was quenched by winding on a chill roll, and then preceded to post-drawing on heated rollers to create an oriented tape. The tapes were drawn in a two-step drawing process. The first drawing step provided some initial orientation, but ultimate drawing was performed in the second step. Multiplication of the first draw ratio, λ_i and the second draw ratio, λ_{ii} gives total draw ratio λ :

$$\lambda = \lambda_i \times \lambda_{ii} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3 shows a bundle of undrawn and drawn tapes, respectively. It should be noted that the drawn tape

is opaque, which is caused by micro-voids in over-drawn highly oriented polymer [18].

2.2 Preparation of PLA/CNT matrix

Multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) were supplied by Nanocyl SA (Belgium). A masterbatch (15 wt.% CNT loading in PLA Natureworks 3051D) was prepared by melt blending in a DSM mini-extruder at 180 °C and 100 rpm for 3 min. This masterbatch was then diluted with pure PLA using the same processing conditions to produce nanocomposites with a desired CNT concentration. After pelletizing and drying, these nanocomposites were hot pressed into matrix films at 180 °C and 50 bars. In this paper, samples were denoted as x CNT, where x represents CNTs weight concentration in PLA matrix.

2.3 Hydrolytic degradation of PLA/CNT matrix

Pre-weighed samples with dimensions 60 mm × 4 mm × 0.15 mm were dried and immersed in vials of distilled water. The vials were then placed in a hot water bath at the degradation temperature 50 °C. At selected immersion periods, specimens were removed from the vials and dried until constant weight.

2.4 Characterization techniques

Tensile tests were performed using an Instron 5586 at room temperature, equipped with a 1 kN load cell at a crosshead speed of 8 mm/min. The reported values were calculated as averages over six specimens.

For the electrical conductivity tests the compression-moulded films were cut into bars. Silver paste was coated on the left and right plane surfaces of the sample to ensure good contacts of the surfaces with the electrodes of the electrometer. The resistance between two silver paste marks along the specimen length direction was measured at room temperature using a Model 6517B Electrometer/High resistance (Keithley instrument Inc, USA). The voltage increased to 30 V at 0.5 V step increase. All current-voltage curves were linear in this study. The volume resistivity was calculated in relation to the specimen dimensions. The measured volume resistance, R_v ,

was converted to volume resistivity, using the formula:

$$\rho = (R_v A) / L \quad (2)$$

Where A is the effective area of the specimen and L is the specimen length. For specimen with a resistivity higher than 10^{10} Ohm, electrical resistivity is not measurable and the films are considered as non-conductive. Three specimens for each composite were tested, and the average value was reported.

Morphological studies were carried out on an FEI Inspector-F scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to investigate the dispersion of MWNTs in nanocomposites. Samples were cold fractured in liquid nitrogen and then gold sputtered before analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Influence of draw ratio on mechanical properties

To produce SR-PLA composites with competitive mechanical properties, it is essential to maximize the mechanical properties of the reinforcing PLA tapes. Tapes were produced with a range of draw ratios, λ , to determine the effect of draw ratio on the mechanical properties of the tapes.

In many publications, the dependence of mechanical properties on the applied draw ratio is described for solid-state drawn fibrous structures, such as fibres, tapes and films. It is commonly concluded that Young's modulus and strength increase with increasing draw ratio, while elongation at break decreases.

Fig. 4 shows typical stress-strain curves of the PLA reinforcement tape prepared at 90 °C upon different draw ratios. The tensile properties are summarized in Table 1. As expected, drawing has a positive effect on modulus and strength of tapes. Compared to isotropic PLA film (1.8 GPa in modulus and 53 MPa in tensile strength), a 141% and 227% increase in Young's modulus and tensile strength have been achieved for the oriented tapes of $\lambda = 7.4$ (4.4 GPa in modulus and 174 MPa in tensile strength), respectively. Furthermore, increasing draw ratio leads to a large decrease in strain to failure. These

results are consistent with what is reported in literatures [19].

3.2 Influence of post drawing temperature on mechanical properties

It was reported that the drawing temperature in the second step can have a dramatic effect on mechanical properties. For this set of tests, tapes were produced at a constant take up speed and increasing drawing temperature in the second step from 70 to 130 °C in 20 °C increments.

From the tensile test data presented (see Fig. 5 and Table 2), a significant influence of post drawing temperature on the overall mechanical behaviour can be seen. Young's modulus and tensile strength of the post drawn tapes increases with post drawing temperature, with maximum values obtained for tapes prepared at 130 °C. The Young's modulus and tensile strength for tapes drawn at 130 °C are 6.7 GPa and 278 MPa, respectively. The values are 467% and 155% higher in modulus and strength compared to tapes drawn at 70 °C. Compared to isotropic PLA films, a 3.7 and 5.2 times increase in Young's modulus and tensile strength has been achieved. Impressively, the elongation at break is also greater than for any of the other tapes. In other words, the tapes drawn at 130 °C have better stiffness, strength, and toughness.

According to an unpublished work, the crystal modulus of poly-L-lactide acid (PLLA) along the chain axis is 12 GPa by using X-ray diffraction [20]. This low value compared to PE is reasonable judging from its helical skeleton (10/3 helix) and large cross-section of a molecule. Therefore, a modulus of 6.7 GPa for a melt-extruded tape is reasonable. Not only compares this well to the theoretical value, but the stiffness reported in this work exceeds the maximum values reported in literatures for melt-spun fibres, which typically lie between 3 and 6 GPa [21, 22].

Fig. 6 compares the mechanical property of SR-PLA reinforcement tape in this research with conventional filler based plastic composites used for semi-structural applications such as automotive parts. The property of SR-PLA bidirectional sheet is forecasted. Although the modulus of SR-PLA sheet is lower than glass fibre filled PP, the tensile strength is quite impressive, and higher than many

traditional filler based polymer composites. Therefore, SR-PLA composites could be of interest for products where strength is critical.

3.3 Nanotube dispersion

The homogeneous dispersion of CNTs in the polymer matrix is one of the most important requirements in achieving conductive nanocomposites. SEM images of fracture surfaces for nanocomposites containing 1 and 5 wt.% CNTs are shown in Fig. 7. CNTs are well dispersed in the PLA matrix without showing noticeable MWNTs aggregates for both nanocomposites.

3.4 Electrical conductivity and percolation threshold

The electrical property of insulating polymers filled with conductive filler is one of the most important physical properties to these composites. The percolation threshold is investigated for composites containing CNTs. As seen in Fig. 8, the percolation threshold is around 0.7 wt.%.

3.5 Degradation sensing

In this section, it is demonstrated how the PLA/CNTs films are not only electrically conductive but also sensitive to degradation stimuli. Fig. 9 shows the resistivity-degradation period dependence of PLA/CNTs films with different filler loadings.

As seen in the Fig. 9, generally the resistivity decreases upon degradation. However, different nanotube concentrations lead to significant differences in sensitivity of the electrical signal.

Resistivity remains almost constant for nanocomposites with 3 wt.% CNTs. Upon lowering the CNT content to 1 wt.%, a slight change in resistivity within one order of magnitude is observed. Similar behaviour is also observed for nanocomposites with 0.8 wt.% CNTs. Here, the change in resistivity is approximately two orders of magnitude, which indicates that a lower CNT concentration makes the system more sensitive. For composite with a CNT loading around the percolation threshold of 0.7 wt.% the resistivity decreases dramatically compared with higher concentrations. Here, the value changes about four

orders of magnitude. Nanocomposites containing CNT concentrations below the percolation threshold (0.5 wt.%) were also investigated to see whether these are more sensitive to degradation. However, here the resistivity value is above 10^6 Ohm.m, which is outside the measurement range for the current experiment set up. The results show that even after 14 days degradation in water the resistivity is still not measurable. There is however a sudden jump in resistivity after 21 days degradation, which becomes constant quickly after that. In other words, the nanocomposites with 0.5 wt.% CNTs seem less sensitive over a wide degradation time range than nanocomposites with 0.7 wt.% CNTs.

Clearly, the composite with a CNT loading around the percolation threshold gives the highest sensitivity and strongest signal.

Many studies have investigated the degradation behaviour of PLA [23]. It is generally accepted that degradation proceeds in two main stages. Water diffuses first into the amorphous regions which are less organized and allow water to penetrate more easily than the highly ordered and densely packed crystalline regions. The second stage starts when most or all of the amorphous regions have been removed and water slowly penetrates the crystalline regions.

When CNTs are blended with semi-crystalline polymers, the CNTs tend to be located in the amorphous phase, since more energy is required for the CNT to disperse in the crystalline phase than that in the amorphous phase [24]. Hence, when during degradation amorphous PLA is removed, this will directly result in a change in CNT network morphology.

In the present study, the observed decrease in resistivity of the CPC, rather than the increase in resistivity as generally observed when sensing most other stimuli such as strain, temperature and vapours, is probably due to an increased CNT network density after removal of (amorphous phase) polymer. Composites containing 3 wt.% CNTs have already a very strong network and hence, polymer degradation does not lead to major changes in local nanotube densities.

In conclusion, the PLA/CNT outer layer of the tape is demonstrated to possess good degradation sensing abilities at CNT concentrations around the percolation threshold, which makes them good candidates for applications in smart biocomposites.

4. Conclusions

SR-PLA composites with degradation sensing have been successfully developed in this pilot research work. The results showed a 3.7 to 5.2 times increase in Young's modulus and tensile strengths for the oriented tapes compared to isotropic PLA film. Through the evolution of electrical conductivity during PLA/CNT compound degradation, we were able to monitor biodegradation of these polymer composites. Composites with a CNT loading around their percolation threshold showed the highest sensitivity and strongest signal.

Ultimately these high strength PLA tapes can be woven into fabrics, which subsequently can be moulded into sheets and thermoformed into complex shaped 3D products, such as shell structure, beams or even sandwich panels when combined with a PLA foam core. These initial results indicate that SR-PLA composites may provide a promising green alternative to commercial polymer composites with embedded smartness.

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Fig. 1. Life cycle of SR-PLA composites.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the hot compaction process for co-extruded tapes.

Fig. 3. The appearance of undrawn and drawn tapes.

Fig. 5. Stress-strain curves of PLA tape post drawn at different temperatures. ($\lambda \approx 8$)

Fig. 4. Stress-strain curves of PLA tape prepared at 90 °C and different draw ratios.

Fig. 6. Comparison of mechanical property for unidirectional tapes and bidirectional SR-PLA composites together with commercial (semi-structural) composites.

Fig. 7. SEM images of (a) 1CNT and (b) 5CNT.

Fig. 8. Change in electrical resistivity with CNT loading for composites film.

Fig. 9. Resistivity of composites film as a function of degradation period.

Table 1. Tensile properties of PLA tapes post drawn at 90 °C and different draw ratios.

Draw ratio	Young's modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Strain at break (%)
1	1.8±0.1	53±2	11±2
3.8	3.5±0.1	157±7	66±9
5.4	4.0±0.2	172±12	41±6
7.4	4.4±0.4	174±13	26±6

Table 2. Tensile properties of PLA tape post drawn at different temperature ($\lambda \approx 8$).

Post drawing temperature (°C)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Strain at break (%)
70	4.6±0.2	109±18	23±4
90	4.4±0.4	174±13	26±6
110	5.8±0.2	248±26	29±9
130	6.7±0.4	278±7	38±4